

Procedure and Results

The air dried and powdered plant material (2 kg) was exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The thick viscous mass so obtained was extracted repeatedly with hexane to remove chlorophyll and fat. The defatted residual mass was extracted with ether. The ether extract on evaporation of the solvent yielded a solid mass. The solid mass was resolved into acidic and neutral fractions by the usual potassium salt method³. The acidic fraction was dissolved in chloroform and passed through a column of silica gel. Elutions with a mixture of methanol and chloroform (1 : 2), yielded compound A, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 316-8° M⁺ 456 and compound B, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$ m.p. 308-10°; M⁺ 456, identified to be betulinic acid and oleanolic acid respectively by comparison of their spectral data⁴ and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The neutral fraction was dissolved in chloroform and passed through a column of silica gel. Successive elutions with mixtures of petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) and benzene : chloroform (1 : 1) yielded compound C, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 198-200° and compound D, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, m.p. 134-36° identified as β -amyrin and β -sitosterol respectively by comparison of i.r. spectra⁵ and m.m.p. with the authentic samples.

The defatted residual mass left after the extraction with ether, was dissolved in methanol and poured into large quantity of ether whereby a dark brown coloured flocculent mass precipitated. The process of dissolution and precipitation was repeated several times in order to purify the coloured mass. It was then decolourised by boiling the methanolic solution of the coloured mass with activated charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to dryness and the solid mass so obtained was dissolved again in a small quantity of methanol and poured again in large quantity of ether whereby a white flocculent mass was precipitated. The precipitate was separated by filtration. On repeated crystallisation from methanol colourless crystals of compound E, $C_{30}H_{48}O_7$, m.p. 206-8°, were obtained, which gave the tests characteristic of saponins⁶. The saponin was hydrolysed with 7% ethanolic sulphuric acid whereupon the sapogenin was precipitated. The sapogenin was separated from the hydrolysate in the usual way and was crystallised from methanol. The sapogenin, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 308-10°, has been characterised as oleanolic acid by comparison of spectral data and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample. The sugar moiety has been found to be rhamnose by co-chromatography with the authentic sample. The quantitative estimation of sugar in the hydrolysate by colorimetric method⁷ revealed the presence of one mole of sugar per mole of saponin. The saponin could not be hydrolysed with 5N NH_4OH which indicates that the COOH group of sapogenin is not involved in glycosidic linkage⁸. Therefore, the OH group at C-3 of oleanolic acid is involved in glycosidic linkage with L-rhamnose. The titrimetric estimation after periodate oxidation of the saponin has revealed that the sugar moiety attached to the

sapogenin is in the pyranose form⁹. Thus, compound E is olean-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl- Δ^{12} -ene-28-oic acid.

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Flavonoid Constituents of the Leaves of *Polygonum glabrum*

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THE plant *Polygonum glabrum* (N. O. Polygonaceae) a small shrub, is widely distributed throughout India¹. The infusion of leaves is used in colic pains and the plant is used as febrifuge². The literature survey of the genus *Polygonum* shows that it is a rich source of flavonoids³⁻⁸ and the flowers of this plant have been examined chemically for the anthocyanins and flavones⁹.

Procedure and Results

The air dried, powdered leaves of *Polygonum glabrum* (2 kg) were extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a thick viscous mass. This was

extracted with hexane to remove fat and chlorophyll. The thick viscous mass left after the extraction with hexane was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a lib-lib mass. The concentrated acetone extract was dissolved in cold water and kept in a refrigerator for a week whereupon a deposit was obtained which was separated by filtration. The solid mass so obtained was dissolved in a small quantity of ethanol and was adsorbed onto a column of magnesol¹⁰. On eluting with ethyl acetate two flavonoid compounds A and B were obtained which were crystallised from acetone: methanol mixture (1 : 1) and methanol respectively.

The compound A, C₁₅H₁₀O₇ (M⁺ 332), m.p. 316° and compound B, C₁₆H₁₂O₇ (M⁺ 316), m.p. 294° were characterised to be quercetin and rhamnetin respectively by m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra with the authentic samples.

The aqueous extract left after the removal of the deposit was concentrated to a thick viscous mass. It was extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was concentrated and adsorbed onto a column of magnesol¹⁰. On eluting with ethyl acetate three flavonoid compounds C, C₂₁H₂₀O₁₁, m. p. 186°, D, C₂₀H₁₈O₁₁, m. p. 217° and E, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆, m. p. 210° were obtained, which were found to be glycosidic in nature. On acid hydrolysis compounds C, D and E gave the same aglycone, m. p. 316° which was identified to be quercetin by m. m. p. with the authentic sample. The hydrolysates from compounds C and D on chromatographic examination revealed the presence of rhamnose and arabinose respectively as sugar moieties while the hydrolysate from compound E showed the presence D-glucose and L-rhamnose. The compounds C, D and E were, therefore, identified as quercitrin, avicularin and rutin, respectively.

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Benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl Dithiocarbonates Potential Pesticides

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S-Benzylthiuronium-O-Alkyl Dithio Carbonates have been prepared by the reaction of carbondisulphide with potassium alkoxides followed by treatment with S-benzylthiuronium chloride. Both the cation and anion are likely to exhibit pesticidal characteristics, as such, these salts are expected to be useful pesticides.

Thiuronium salts^{1,2} possess pesticidal properties. Trithiocarbonates³, dithiocarbonates^{4,6}, S-dimethylthiocarbamoyl dithiocarbonates⁷, thiocarbonates⁸ and carbonates⁹ have been used as pesticides. Thiuronium salts of O-alkyl dithiocarbonic acids in which both the ions have biocidal characteristics, are expected to be valuable pesticides. The preparation of benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl dithiocarbonates was, therefore, undertaken. The salts can be prepared in good yields with great ease. The details of the preparation are as follows. Their decomposition points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I—BENZYLTHIURONIUM-O-ALKYL DITHIOCARBONATES DERIVED FROM VARIOUS ALCOHOLS.

Alcohol	*d.p. of salt °C	% Sulphur		%Nitrogen	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Methyl	75	35.14	35.64	10.26	10.02
Ethyl	80	33.44	33.38	9.76	9.81
n-Propyl	87	31.87	31.87	9.30	9.25
iso-Propyl	104	31.87	32.47	9.30	9.00
n-Butyl	95	30.46	30.37	8.89	8.89
iso-Butyl	83	30.46	30.86	8.89	8.25
iso-Amyl	95	29.16	29.06	8.51	8.11
Benzyl	84	27.49	27.60	8.02	8.56
Cyclohexyl	106	28.13	28.54	8.21	7.61

*Decomposition points are uncorrected.